

The safety margin of extraction is 5 min within which period nickel is quantitatively extracted in a single operation.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity

The molar absorptivity of the complex is 1.08×10^4 and 1.02×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 400 and 360 nm respectively (on the basis of nickel content) and sensitivity of the colour reaction (in terms of Sandell's definition) is 0.005 µg Ni/cm².

Stability of the colour

The absorbance of the chloroform solution of the Ni(II)-benzil- α -monoxime complex, prepared according to the general procedure at pH 9, was measured at 400 nm at elapsed times of 30 min, 1, 6, 12, 24 & 36 hours. The corresponding absorbances indicate that the colour is stable at least for 24 hours, at the end of 36 hours the absorbance decreases by about 4%. Hence it is suggested that the optical density be measured within 24 hours after the extraction.

Reagent concentration

Keeping the variables constant the concentration and amount of acetic solution of the benzil- α -monoxime was varied. It has been found that about 20-fold excess of the reagent is the requisite to operate the extraction process.

1 ml of 1% acetic solution of the reagent is sufficient to serve the purpose below which the extraction is found to be incomplete. The absorbance is more or less constant even if 2ml of 2% solution is used.

Effect of diverse ions

The following ions may be tolerated when present in amounts (µg) shown in parentheses to determine 50.6 µg Ni at pH 9: ruthenium(III) (500), palladium(II) (500), mercury(II) (1000), lead(II) (1000), lithium(I) (1000), magnesium(II) (2000), calcium(II) (2000), strontium(II) (2000), barium(II) (2000), lanthanum(III) (1500), rhodium(III) (500), platinum(IV) (500), zinc(II) (1500), cerium(III) (500), uranium(VI) (1000), tungsten(VI) (700), arsenic(III) (800).

Presence of cadmium(II), iron(III), osmium(VIII), copper(II), beryllium(II), zirconium(IV), chromium(II), aluminium(III), thorium(IV) results incomplete extraction. Manganese(II), cobalt(II), vanadium(V) impart high results.

Among the anions tested, chloride (3000), bromide (1000), thiocyanate (2500), iodide(500), thiosulphate (1000), oxalate (2000), borate(4000), tartrate (4000), phosphate (4000) do not interfere in the extraction procedure. However EDTA and fluoride interfere rather seriously.

Precision and accuracy

In six such runs with 50.6 µg Ni(II), the relative mean deviation in the absorbances found, was $\pm 1.7\%$. Different amounts of Ni(II) were taken and determined by the recommended procedure. The results are accurate to within $\pm 2.4\%$.

Thus the process is rapid, simple and a fairly satisfactory one requiring only 20-25 min for each run.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Mr. G. Biswas, Department of Chemistry, Siliguri College, Darjeeling for his kind assistance, Prof. H. N. Khastgir, Head of the Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, for extending full laboratory facilities and the University Grant Commission, India for financial support.

References

1. A. K. De, S. M. Khopkar and R. A. Chalmers, *Solvent extraction of metals*, (VNR Co., London), 1970.
2. P. K. Paria and S.K. Majumdar, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1976, 278, 364.
3. P. K. Paria and S. K. Majumdar, *Ind. J. Chem.* (in press).
4. K. Ueda, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, 92, 1160.
5. A. I. Vogel, *A text book of practical organic chemistry*, (Orient Longmans, London), 1973, p 720.
6. A.I. Vogel, *A text book of quantitative inorganic analysis*. (Orient Longmans, London), 1969, p 479.

Chalcones XXIII : Studies on Potential Germicides Derived from Substituted Methyl Aryl Ketones.

SHYAM SUNDER MISRA*

Deptt. of Chemistry, F. G. College, Rae Bareilly 229001

and

SANTOSH C. KUSHWAHA

Department of Chemistry Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur-208002.

Manuscript received 29 March 1976, revised 11 October 1976, accepted 10 February 1977

PPROMISING usefulness of chalcones and their analogues as bactericides, ^{2,6, 23, 24}, insecticides, ^{11, 12, 20} germicides, ^{7-9, 16-19}, cardiovascular, sedative ^{1, 2, 5}, antifertility¹⁰, etc. agents have been reported. Wilson and coworkers¹⁰ used these compounds to protect adrenaline from destruction. Hydroxy chalcones possess¹⁵ increased antimicrobial activity without damaging the host tissues. Gowan and Brian also observed²¹ fungistatic action of heterocyclic chalcones on *A. niger* at low concen-

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYSIS OF CHALCONES.

Ar—CH=CH—CO—Ar'								
Ar	Ar'	Colour & crystals.	M. P. °C	Yield Chal. 2 : 4-DNP	%	Halochromism	$\nu_{\max} >C=O$	Dia-of zone, inhb. mm
2-Br	2-thienyl	LYN	267	—	68	Red	1668	12
4-Br	2 thienyl ^a	SYN	130	—	72	Orange	1653	12
6-Br 3 : 4-(O-CH ₃) ₂	2 thienyl ^b	YN	192	217	65	Pink	—	10
6-Br 3 : 4-(O-CH ₃ -O)	2 thienyl	SYN	136	187	63	Brown	—	9
6-NO ₂ -3:4-(OCH ₃) ₂	2-thienyl	LYP	165	241	57	Red	—	8
2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde	2-thienyl	YNo	159	213	43	Dark Brown	—	—
2-OMe	1-naphthyl ^a	SNo	161	—	69	Pink	1672	—
3-OMe	1-naphthyl	SP	154	—	63	Red	—	—
5-Br-4-OH-3-OMe	1-naphthyl ^b	CN	149	—	71	Greenish	1668	8
2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde	1-naphthyl	SP	147	211D	58	Brown	—	—
2 Br	4-biphenyl ^a	LYP	140	—	82	Orange	1665	10
4-Br	4-biphenyl ^a	SYP	201	219	87	Bloodred	—	11
2 : 6-Cl ₂	4-biphenyl	LYN	126	251	90	Bloodred	—	11
2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde	4-biphenyl	YP	138	—	51	Cherryred	—	—
1-naphthaldehyde	4-biphenyl ^b	SN	141	198	69	Pink	—	—
6-Br-3:4-(O-CH ₃ -O)	4-biphenyl	LYN	143	—	73	Red	—	8

*All melting points were recorded in open capillary and hence uncorrected.

L=light; Y=yellow; N=needles; No=nodules, S=silvery; P=plates, C=colourless

Crystallised from a=dioxane; b=ethyl acetate.

tration. These observations have encouraged the authors to synthesise, a series of homocyclic and heterocyclic chalcones by the method reported^{2,3,4} earlier, condensing 4-phenyl acetophenone, 1-acetonaphthone and 2-acetothienone with various aryl aldehydes under the specified conditions.

Experimental

2-acetyl thiophene, 1-acetyl naphthalene and 4-phenyl acetophenone were condensed with equimolar quantities of benzaldehydes in presence of sodium ethoxide and aldehyde free alcohol by the method of Misra^{2,4}. Naphthyl and biphenyl chalcones were obtained by cold condensation whereas thienyl chalcones by hot condensation. Reactants were refluxed along with 15-30% aqueous KOH solution for 8-10 hours and then cooled to ice temperature. The deposited compounds were collected, and washed with cold alcohol and crystallised. Filtrate on treatment with crushed ice and 10% HCl gave a little more compound which after usual treatment was crystallised from ethyl alcohol unless otherwise mentioned.

Biochemical Screening

Germicidal characteristics were studied by agar-cup method *in vitro*, using beef extract-peptone-agar

References

1. K. K. Hsu and F. C. Chen, *Tiwan K' Hsueh*, 1973, 27, 236.
2. S. S. Misra and Bhola Nath, *Indian J. App. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 200.
3. S. S. Misra and J. B. Lal, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1970, 40, 296.
4. H. P. Buu-Hoi and N. D. Xuong, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 1646.
5. S. C. Kushwaha, S. S. Misra and J. B. Lal, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1970, 40, 301.
6. S. S. Misra, *Labdev J. Sci. & Tech.* (India), 1971, 8A, 152.

solid nutrient broth media^{2,3} at pH 7.4 in presterilised petri dishes. The bacteria selected for studies included *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* which are common in growth of cereal crops. The activity is reported by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition in mm. at $32 \pm 2^\circ$. after 24 hr.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to authorities of H.B.T.I., Kanpur for providing necessary facilities, Director, C.D.R.I., Lucknow for elemental analysis, biochemical screening and ir spectra, Mrs. Bimla Misra for her cooperation and also to Sri G.N. Misra for help.

7. W. S. Ceiger and J. E. Conn, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 112,
8. S. S. Misra, *Indian J. App. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 211.
9. S. S. Misra and Dinkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 40, 637.
10. C. W. Wilson and D. E. Floyd, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1949, 49, 399.
11. S. S. Misra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1973, 50, 335.
12. S. S. Misra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 68.
13. S. S. Misra, *Monat. fur Chemie*, 1973, 104, 11.
14. S. S. Misra and Bhola Nath, *Indian J. App. Chem.*, 1972, 35, 95.
15. N. Narasimhachari and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 128.
16. S. S. Misra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 909.
17. S. S. Misra and Dinkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 556.
18. S. S. Misra and S. C. Kushwaha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 564.
19. S. Ambekar, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1961, 13, 698.
20. S. S. Misra and Dinkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 639.
21. M. Gowan and J. Brian, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1949, 49, 9334b.
22. Naxlevie, An Introduction to Laboratory Techniques in Bacteriology The Macmillan Co, N, Y, 1954.
23. S. C. Kushwaha, Dinkar, & J. B. Lal, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 82.
24. R. Kuhn and H. R. Hensel, *Chem. Ber.* 1953, 86, 1333.